

**TOOLING AND TOOLING AIDS FOR FIBRE REINFORCED
POLYMERIC COMPOSITE MOULDINGS (AND FOR COMBINING
SOME OF THESE WITH HONEYCOMB STRUCTURED AND OTHER
REINFORCEMENT), WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO LARGE
(MAINLY NICKEL) ELECTROFORMED TOOLING.**

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BASIS AND ABSTRACT

Composites being, by definition, not homogeneous materials, their qualities and those of the articles moulded from them, are strongly affected by the mode (technical level) of processing material and article. Apart from mixing, metering, laying up, etc, the quality of the tooling which shapes and forms the article is thus particularly critical.

A number of alternative types of tooling are mentioned and, in part, described. The point of view that (mainly nickel) electroformed tooling - with the development of which one writer has been associated since 1940, even modestly involving Imperial College resources at early stages - often forms the expedient means of producing relatively large composite objects will be explained and illustrated by slides and samples, mainly in the course of the oral presentation, the main purpose of which will be to invite an exchange of experience and views on tooling for composites.

A provisional appreciation of PEEK thermoplastics composites, their potential importance, and resulting tooling aspects, is inserted in to the paper just like these materials are seeking a place in existing methodology.

1.0 INTRODUCTION, A CONCEPT OF COMPOSITES

The term composites is applied here to objects made from fibre reinforced polymeric resins, mostly thermosetting and some

thermoplastic. Epoxyde, polyester and phenolic (lately back in favour because of good fire behaviour¹) are the principal thermosetting resins referred to. Polyurethane and Nylon are the thermoplastic ones, the processes envisaged being RRIM and MMRIM²). The reinforced fibres: Carbon (acrylic based), aramide (nylon based) and glass, all in various discrete and random orientations. When these are linked to metal, say in an aeroplane aileron, consisting of a moulded thermosetting skin densely reinforced by rigidly oriented carbon fibres, wrapped around aluminium honeycomb material filled with polymeric foam, we have an even more 'composite' composite, made possible by tooling of various kinds to be described in more detail.

2.0 TYPES OF TOOLING RELATED TO MOULDING PROCESSES

Most of the composite articles envisaged (eg for aircraft, automobiles, see below) are, relatively thin walled, hollow bodies and, in the case of thermosetting resin base, tooling can be divided into one sided and two sided; using the analogy of a ham sandwich with the ham as moulding and bread as tool, a single sided tool would compare with an open sandwich. (Not quite the same as one or two part tooling, there can be a one sided two part tool, eg for an undercut shape.) This differentiation also divides the moulding processes:

one sided tools: lay ups, rubber bagged autoclave mouldings, sometimes using 'prepreg' materials.

two sided tools: compression/injection moulding (low pressure), sometimes with inlaid mats, etc.

The thermoplastic resin processes already referred to call for two sided tooling, often 'matched metal moulds'. (But now see next section.)

3.0 ENTER THE HIGH TEMPERATURE THERMOPLASTICS³)

Continuous carbon fibre reinforced PEEK (polyether ether ketone) thermoplastics sheet, a higher form of prepreg, rivals or complements long fibre reinforced thermosetting resin components for high strength

requirements. It breaks, conceptually, out of the previous dichotomy of short fibres/thermoplastics, long fibres/thermosets.

3.1 Tooling Aspects: Being of high molecular sophistication, these materials are expensive and must add economic to their technical justification by faster cycling and otherwise expedient moulding and trimming processes. Thin walled but rigid matched metal moulds ("two sided") of high thermal conductivity kept alternating between around 390°C (flat sheet-deformation/moulding) and around 340°C (shaped sheet-rigidity/ejection) appear to be the best way to produce shell like, robust components from a sheet material permitting use at up to 250°C. The move, however incomplete, in the direction of sheet metal working technology, is something the motor industry, for instance, always welcomes.

Thermal cycling within a relatively narrow band of temperatures should also attenuate problems arising from differing coefficients of tool and polymer material expansion, problems which worry some users, also in the aircraft industry, though evidence of the practical impact of this is hard to come by.

Evenly thin (2 - 3 mm) electroformed nickel shells, supported by rigid but dimensionally adjustable structures (see 7.1), their rear (non-moulding) surfaces accessible to hot and cold air blasts and/or oven atmospheres, promise to be an appropriate tooling approach for this technology.

3.2 Historical Perspective Note: The PEEK/carbon fibre technology described (the material is also referred to as Thermoplastic Aromatic Polymer Composite, APC-2) holds out hope of more automated production of contoured high performance composite outer skins on their own. On the other hand, one of the development perspectives of the motor industry is to combine greater use of polymeric composites, and of manufacturing automation of these, by producing outer skin and inner linings and fittings simultaneously (combining moulding and assembly), a true composite if ever there was one. A boot lid (boot = trunk in USA) leaving the RIM moulding station complete with lock and

hinges in position might be an example. Obvious opportunities for automated handling technology. Maybe, the marriage between automated composite skin forming and that of automated "skin plus content" can come about via MMRIM (see note to Ref. 2). This line of thought is pursued under **9.0 CONCLUSION.**

4.0 TOOL MAKING PROCESSES AND TOOL MATERIALS

Desirable tool qualities include accuracy, durability, low cost, ease of tool manipulation, often thermal conductivity. Tools are made from wood, reinforced resin, plaster, combinations of the last three, light metal castings, sheet metal fabrications.

Solid machined steel tools can usually be discounted for cost and weight reasons. Thin walled fibre reinforced resin tooling, ie composite tooling for composites, has lately been tried, the hope of greater durability than other resin tooling and the low coefficient of thermal expansion being an attraction, particularly in the case of carbon fibre reinforced tooling.

Choice of tool making method and material will be influenced by which of the previously mentioned desirable qualities represent the predominant need in a particular case (number of pieces wanted, etc). Electroformed nickel often offers the best compromise, being accurate and economical.

All these tool making methods, in some cases even machined steel, and with the possible exception of tools fabricated from sheet metal, share the need for initially having a positive model or prototype, replica of at least one face of the future composite, as part of the tool making process. Very often this, conveniently, also forms a requirement of the design process and is thus not an additional cost.

5.0 ELECTROFORMED TOOLING FOR COMPOSITES⁴⁾

Electroforming is electroplating continued for sufficient time (and with sufficient know-how) to create a metallic skin of adequate thickness and strength to be largely self supporting after separation

from its basis or master to fulfil the duties for which it has been formed.

In historic sequence, mould electroforming used mainly copper, then electrodeposited iron, then nickel (1890 - 1950+, approx.).

Contemporary mould electroforming for composites means electro-deposition, as even as possible, of 2 - 4 mm nickel on to a bath master, the latter being, over at least part of its surface, a three dimensional mirror image of the working surface of the future tool, ie a virtual replica of at least one face of the future composite.

5.1 Electrodeposition permits metal property variations different from those achievable by other metallurgical processes and dependent on plating bath composition and plating conditions. For the tooling work described, a tough, ductile grade of nickel (250 VPH) rather than the harder deposit of 47 Rc (used for smaller tooling for thermoplastics) is usually preferred, though succeeding layers of the two nickels (hard first = ultimate working surface) are used to tool for some large composites.

(There is, inter alia, the option of backing the nickel with further millimetres of reverse current plated copper of almost the hardness of the ductile nickel - an option less often taken up in recent practice, unless quartz filled thermosetting resins as used for quality kitchenware (multiple sinks) are counted as composites.)

5.2 The most recommended master material for large electroformed tooling is cast epoxy resin (the surface made conductive by a chemical silver mirror), its stability against deformation ensured not only by filling (except the gelcoat surface) but by incorporated supporting metal structures and other design features. Master casting has the economic advantage of easy reproduction from wooden or other prototypes, but contour machined ('die-sunk') large masters from solid polymeric materials such as UREOL 450 made by CIBA-GEIGY have, lately, also been used.

5.3 The maximum size of electroformed tooling for composites depends on the size of the electroplating tanks, the ampère capacity of low voltage current available to these tanks and the lifting tackle erected above them. The plant with the work of which the writers are associated (believed to be the world's largest and the oldest established in Europe) at present accepts masters 9 m long and 3 m wide, or more than 25 m² surface, in tanks of more than 50,000 litres of working volume.

5.4 Although the nickel shell tooling described is sufficiently rigid to be virtually self supporting, some form of backing is usually expedient in the interest of ease of mould handling (ultimately, automated opening and closing), dimensional accuracy and support against moulding pressure, heating/cooling, etc. Fabricated or cast metal structures, bonded to the nickel by resin, welding or screwing, alternatively cast resin, plaster or cement are among the choices of backing/support, as are combinations of these. (See also 7.1.)

6.0 APPLICATIONS OF ELECTROFORMED TOOLING (COMPOSITES)

6.1 Nickel electroformed moulds for large aircraft radomes (GRP) were first used in the USA in the 1950's. In Europe, during the last 15 years, the aircraft industry has been the major user of electroformed nickel tooling (besides resin and sheet metal tools). This development has been accentuated by the extension of the use of composites beyond aircraft parts of tertiary stress (interior lining panels) to those of secondary stress requirements, ie parts of the outer skin, not only radomes (likewise missile cones) but ailerons, rudders, stabilisers and other guided devices, also wing surface sections⁵).

Figure 1. Nickel electroformed tool with welded steel support for Airbus A300/310 radome, resin 'bath master' just being extracted.

6.2 In the motor industry, including the manufacture of commercial vehicles, composites have been used for outer panels, including very large sections amounting to half a car body shell, elastomeric internal linings (dash boards), semi resilient (RRIM) external parts, bumpers, 'front' or 'rear' 'ends', wheel arches etc. Still feeling its way towards the even more polymeric car, the motor industry uses large resin, nickel electroformed and machined steel tools.

Composites will really come of age, volume and production method wise, with future requirements of the motor industry and it is hoped that discussion induced by this paper, will play a part, however tiny, in speeding this development.

Figure 2. Nickel electroformed tool, backed by steel frame and resin, for FORD Escort front end.

7.0 RECENT ADVANCES IN THE FIELD OF ELECTROFORMED TOOLING FOR COMPOSITES

7.1 Rigid but dimensionally adjustable (to compensate mainly for distortion through polymerisation) profiled mould surfaces obtained by spot welding internally threaded stainless steel bushes to the back of 3 - 5 mm thick nickel mould faces and marrying these to welded steel support structures via turnable bolts engaging the bushes. (Theoretically possible not only with electroformed but also with, albeit shallow, sheet metal tools.)

This, ie the welding of threaded bushes to the back of electroformed mould shells, providing facility for support plus marginally adjustable dimensions, is becoming standard Galvanoform practice.

7.2. Formers of slender positive ('male') near aerofoil shape (leading

edge trailing off into parallel planes) to enable carbon fibres to be laid up densely in resin without a weakening parting line. This involves 'deep throw' electroforming (if done in metal) of a, previously unachieved, depth to width ratio through new plating circuit technology.

Slides showing such an aerofoil former and recently made and used large moulds for composites, as well as some demonstration pieces, will form the main content of the oral presentation.

8.0 ELECTROFORMED SPARK EROSION (E.D.M.) ELECTRODES

These are considered here for finishing the surfaces of tools for moulding composites and for shaping the metal structures going into such composites.

8.1 Given a positive prototype of the ultimate composite shape, electroforming an electrode to 'burn' (EDM - Electric Discharge Machining) this shape into a block of metal to form a tool, requires even one less step than electroforming the tool itself because one negative casting step can be omitted. Suitably and rigidly supported and provided with datum faces, contact points, where necessary rinsing channels for the dielectric fluid, ie ready to mount on an EDM machine (illustration), such electrodes, used as an alternative or complement to engraved graphite electrodes, may bring steel tooling nearer economic viability as a means of moulding composites needed in large quantities.

8.2 Having established techniques of making and using electroformed EDM electrodes of contoured shape, it was natural to try and then establish that these could burn away the top portions of the walls of the hexagonal cells of light alloy honeycomb structures in order, for instance, to give their notional boundary planes aerofoil or other curvatures. This is all the easier and more economical, as bath masters or steps towards them are likely to be available from the toolmaking for the resin-fibre composites of the same curvatures to be wrapped around the honeycomb fillings and all the more attractive

as there is no satisfactory other (cutting) method of generating these curvatures along the edges of spaced sheet metal 'walls'. It is hoped to show examples of the application of this technology, which is still being developed and might, in due course be of interest to sandwich composite applications also outside the aircraft industry. However, this development comes at a time when the aircraft industry tends to replace light alloy honeycomb material by non-metallic honeycomb and similar matrices, ie composites within composites.

9.0 CONCLUSION

The motor car and aerospace industries are now seeking major manufacturing economies through the ability to finish a complete item, rather than sub-components of an item, ex mould.

The future of mass produced high quality composites (with surface finish as an important quality parameter in addition to strength), needed by the motor industry even more than by aircraft manufacture (numbers), must involve control technology (pick and place, in addition to metering, mixing, timing also of thermal control), probably electronic/pneumatic. Equally probably it is likely to involve nickel electroformed tooling.

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